

Nutrient status of some rice soils

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We evaluated fertilizer needs of high yielding rice varieties. Soil samples were collected from 23 locations in the districts of Dhaka, Tangail, Faridpur, Kustia, and Jessore. Low fertilizer levels as urea, triple superphosphate, and muriate of

potash were applied for 2 to 6 years. Sometimes cow dung also was applied.

Leaf blade samples taken from boro crops of IR3 and IR8 at panicle initiation and soil samples collected in May and Jun 1978 were dried and analyzed for nutrient content.

Table 1 presents average values for soil pH, percent organic matter, total N, available P, ammonium acetate extractable K, Ca, and Mg, Ca (H₂PO₄)₂ extractable S, and 0.1N HCl extractable Zn.

Soil pH varied from moderately acid 5.4 to moderately alkaline 8.2. Organic matter ranged from 1.16 to 2.86%, averaging 1.94%. Total N content varied between 0.08 and 0.16%, averaging 0.124%. Soils were generally poor in organic matter and total N, but C—N ratios favored rice production (Table 1).

Available P content ranged from low to high. Available K averaged 0.76 meq/100 g soil and available Ca, 14.13 meq/100 g soil. Available Mg ranged from 1.40

Table 1. Some physiochemical characteristics of the soils at 23 locations in Bangladesh.

Location	Textural class (with % clay)	pH	Organic matter (%)	Total N (%)	Available nutrients						C:N
					meq/100 g			ppm			
					K	Ca	Mg	Zn	P	S	
Ghumi ₁ , Tangail	Silty clay (45.7)	6.15	1.50	0.12	0.94	6.20	3.24	4.31	7.50	10.28	7.25
Ghumi ₂ , Tangail	Silty clay (44.8)	6.20	2.43	0.14	0.84	6.34	2.92	4.10	35.00	9.24	10.00
Kalihati ₁ , Tangail	Silty clay (44.2)	5.80	1.33	0.10	0.92	6.10	1.20	5.20	41.88	9.38	7.70
Kalihati ₂ , Tangail	Silty clay loam (38.7)	5.65	1.16	0.12	0.85	4.28	2.10	3.90	43.75	11.20	7.25
Sathalia, Tangail	Clay loam (39.2)	6.60	2.20	0.15	0.70	5.34	1.90	4.18	50.00	10.24	8.50
Kalmeshwar, Dhaka	Silty clay loam (27.7)	6.20	1.24	0.09	0.40	7.00	2.10	5.10	53.13	7.80	7.99
Majpara ₁ , Dhaka	Clay (63.0)	6.00	2.24	0.14	0.91	20.10	2.31	6.20	2.50	14.20	7.28
Majpara ₂ , Dhaka	Clay loam (35.6)	5.90	2.37	0.15	0.50	17.10	3.10	4.90	21.88	14.12	9.16
Rarikhal ₁ , Dhaka	Clay (62.1)	6.10	2.86	0.15	0.58	19.00	3.24	6.18	18.75	13.12	11.00
Rarikhal ₂ , Dhaka	Clay (62.0)	6.15	1.62	0.12	0.73	21.30	3.90	5.27	11.00	14.18	7.83
Matlagram ₁ , Dhaka	Clay (65.2)	5.50	2.24	0.14	1.20	17.30	2.39	5.70	11.00	15.10	9.28
Matlagram ₂ , Dhaka	Clay (69.3)	6.20	1.99	0.13	0.84	18.10	2.13	6.18	15.00	14.10	8.88
Juair, Faridpur	Silty clay loam (40.8)	7.80	2.37	0.12	0.70	18.70	3.10	4.28	8.75	29.20	10.60
Bhakindapur, Faridpur	Clay loam (42.3)	8.10	1.49	0.09	0.81	19.20	3.04	3.23	11.25	18.23	9.56
Alipur, Faridpur	Clay loam (38.5)	8.15	1.49	0.08	0.72	17.20	2.90	2.84	8.75	21.20	10.70
Bhakindagram ₁ , Faridpur	Clay (50.4)	8.20	1.37	0.08	0.84	18.50	2.49	5.20	10.00	18.30	9.88
Bhakindagram ₂ , Faridpur	Clay (49.7)	8.10	1.74	0.10	0.76	19.30	2.41	3.10	10.00	26.38	10.00
Amjupi, Kustia	Sandy clay (41.30)	7.15	2.61	0.12	0.64	17.20	2.29	2.18	21.25	19.32	12.60
Rajnagar, Kustia	Sandy clay (43.4)	8.00	1.49	0.12	0.81	21.00	3.10	3.38	10.00	22.14	8.25
Tetulia, Kustia	Clay loam (45.1)	7.10	2.49	0.13	0.59	13.10	2.20	2.58	5.00	20.13	11.10
Ulashi, Jessore	Clay loam (38.50)	5.40	1.97	0.14	0.60	9.13	1.04	3.30	3.80	12.34	8.16
Pathila, Jessore	Silty clay (45.9)	7.50	2.37	0.16	0.71	12.10	1.84	2.18	7.50	17.15	8.59
Dattanagar, Jessore	Clay loam (40.2)	7.00	2.12	0.16	0.84	11.10	1.90	3.29	5.00	30.14	7.69

to 3.90 meq/100 g soil. These are adequate amounts for successful rice production.

Available S was between 7.80 and 30.14 ppm. Soils of Ghumi₂ and Kalihati of Tangail District and Kalmeshwar of Dhaka District were S deficient. Available Zn (2.18-6.20 ppm) is adequate for rice culture.

N content of the leaf blades ranged from 1.32 to 3.07% and P from 0.008 to 0.140% (Table 2). Almost all plants showed N and P deficiency. K content of the plant tissue ranged from 0.39 to 1.79%. Only plants from Majpara had K deficiency. Ca content of leaves ranged from 0.20 to 0.44%. The Ca content of leaves collected from Ghumi₁, Kalihati₂, and Sathalia was low. Mg varied between 0.10 and 0.17%, and all leaf samples showed deficiency. Leaf samples from Tangail and Kalemshwar were S deficient (Table 2). Zn concentration ranged from 12.3 to 58.7 ppm, averaging 29.6 ppm.

Data on soil and plant nutrients indicated that all the soils had N and P deficiency. With few exceptions, soils contained adequate K. Soil analysis indi-

Table 2. Nutrient composition of rice leaf at panicle initiation stage.

Place	Dry matter yield in g (50 leaves)	Nutrient elements in leaf blades						
		N (%)	P (%)	K (%)	Ca (%)	Mg (%)	S (%)	Zn (ppm)
Ghumi ₁	5.0524	1.78	0.014	1.56	0.28	0.14	0.04	32.70
Ghumi ₂	6.3795	1.96	0.034	1.29	0.21	0.12	0.04	45.30
Kalihati ₁	4.1650	1.54	0.014	1.64	0.24	0.12	0.05	40.00
Kalihati ₂	5.7970	3.07	0.048	1.36	0.29	0.14	0.04	41.40
Sathalia	7.1834	2.05	0.018	1.48	0.22	0.10	0.05	31.30
Kalmeshwar	5.2680	1.72	0.027	1.01	0.20	0.12	0.03	33.00
Majpara ₁	3.9700	3.06	0.008	1.48	0.38	0.15	0.11	55.70
Majpara ₂	5.9030	2.31	0.014	0.39	0.30	0.15	0.13	27.70
Rarikhal ₁	4.2365	2.60	0.014	1.68	0.32	0.14	0.10	58.70
Rarikhal ₂	5.1780	2.65	0.009	1.72	0.34	0.15	0.12	42.00
Matlagram ₁	6.4060	1.96	0.018	1.01	0.35	0.15	0.11	45.40
Matlagram ₂	5.2665	2.81	0.008	1.60	0.35	0.14	0.14	45.00
Juair	5.4730	1.74	0.018	1.21	0.38	0.14	0.14	21.00
Bhakindapur	4.2470	1.72	0.014	1.21	0.41	0.15	0.10	15.30
Alipur	4.4180	1.79	0.019	1.20	0.38	0.16	0.12	17.30
Bhakindagram ₁	4.3230	1.72	0.010	1.24	0.44	0.15	0.13	27.70
Bhakindagram ₂	3.2370	1.73	0.008	0.94	0.42	0.16	0.14	24.00
Amjupi	4.3355	1.32	0.018	1.44	0.44	0.17	0.13	21.00
Rajnagar	3.6720	1.62	0.014	1.79	0.40	0.16	0.11	24.00
Tetulia	2.2795	2.22	0.012	1.48	0.38	0.16	0.14	12.30
Ulashi	5.7065	1.24	0.010	1.01	0.40	0.13	0.11	21.00
Pathila	5.3240	2.31	0.017	1.21	0.41	0.15	0.18	18.70
Dattanagar	3.4950	1.45	0.014	1.13	0.35	0.15	0.18	16.30

cated there was an adequate supply of available Ca and Mg in all the areas, but plant analysis showed crops in Ghumi₁, Ghumi₂, Kalihati₁, Kalihati₂, and Satha-

lia to be Ca deficient. Plant analysis showed Zn deficiency in all the areas though soil analysis indicated adequate Zn supply. □

Nitrogen management in rainfed lowland transplanted rice grown on calcareous soil

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The effect of applying different nitrogen sources was studied at the RAU Research Farm during 1981 kharif. Nitrogen sources were prilled urea, lac-coated urea (LCU), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and urea supergranules (USG). A no-nitrogen control and 29, 58, and 87 kg N/ha were applied in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Soil in the field was a calcareous silt loam with 0.76% organic carbon, 8.8 kg available P/ha, 0.12 meq/100 g exchangeable K, and pH 7.9.

Thirty-five-day-old Pankaj seedlings were transplanted at 15- × 20-cm spacing on 23 Jul 1981. Prilled urea was applied either basally or in 3 equal splits at transplanting, tillering, and panicle initiation.

Rough rice yield as influenced by sources and levels of nitrogen.

Source of N	Grain yield (t/ha)				LSD 5%
	29 (kg N/ha)	58 (kg N/ha)	87 (kg N/ha)	Mean	
Prilled urea (basal)	3.3	3.4	3.7	3.4	Source (S) - 0.22
Prilled urea (split)	3.3	3.5	3.9	3.6	N level (N) - 0.17
Lac-coated urea	2.9	3.2	3.6	3.2	S × N - NS
Sulfur-coated urea	3.4	3.7	4.0	3.7	Control vs - 0.14
Urea supergranules	3.4	3.9	4.0	3.7	rest
Mean	3.3	3.5	3.8		
No-N control		2.91			

LCU (34% N) and SCU (36.7% N) having 21% dissolution rate in 7 days were broadcast and incorporated before transplanting. USG were placed 8-10 cm deep between 4 hills immediately after transplanting when the soil began to harden. All plots received a basal dose of 18 kg P and 17 kg K/ha, and a 0.5% ZnSO₄ solution with lime was sprayed on the crop at tillering stage. Drought from heading through harvest reduced yield. After

harvesting a net area of 10.88 m² on 17 Nov grain yield was recorded at 14% moisture.

Averaged over three nitrogen levels, SCU, USG, and split-applied prilled urea produced yields significantly superior to those from basally applied prilled urea and LCU (see table). Grain yield increased significantly with each increase in applied N. Although the interaction between sources and levels of N was not signif-